

Assessment of Artificial Intelligence (AI) on Media Practitioners' Creativity and Capacity Development

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ABSTRACT: Artificial intelligence (AI) is an innovative and modern technology that enables computers to perform tasks that typically require human-like intelligence. In January, 2025, empirical report showed that Nigeria surpasses global average with 70% AI adoption rate. The report said Nigeria's online population is leading the global adoption of generative AI, with 70 percent of respondents reporting usage, far exceeding the global average of 48 percent. With this report, Nigerians dependence on AI is quite alarming and it is of believe that AI is gradually taken over human creativity and existence.

The study adopted survey method and in-depth Interview research methods with a focus on 120 respondents for the survey method and three (3) media practitioners for the in-depth-interview that cut across print, broadcast and online media in three selected states (Osun, Oyo and Lagos) in South-West, Nigeria. One editor from print media outfits, one editor from broadcast media and one respondent from online news outlets who were purposively selected based on their knowledge and experience in the field of journalism.

The study found out that AI has come to stay in modern world and it is very essential in different fields most especially field of journalism. Finding also indicated that when applied improperly or excessively, AI increases the efficiency and some of the skills but poses a threat to originality, depth, and standards.

The study therefore concludes that AI is a strong supporting system but not a substitute of human journalists. A balanced integration, ethical standards, and long-term capacity building can help the Nigerian media to embrace the benefits of AI and remain creative, accurate, and trusted by the people. The study recommends that media organizations ought to ensure that all their staff are trained on the ways of using AI intelligently, as an assistant and not a thinking substitute.

KEYWORDS: Artificial Intelligence, Assessment, Implication, Creativity, Capacity Development.

INTRODUCTION

Artificial intelligence (AI) is an innovative and modern technology that enables computers to perform tasks that typically require human-like intelligence. AI accepts and decodes words, analyze data, and make appropriate recommendations. Artificial Intelligence (AI), is typically the ability of a digital computer or computer-controlled robot to perform tasks commonly associated with intelligent beings. The term is commonly applied to the project of developing systems endowed with the intellectual processes characteristic of humans, such as the ability to reason, discover meaning, generalize, or learn from past experience (Copeland, 2025). AI refers to the ability of a computer or machine to mimic the competencies of the human mind, which often learns from previous experiences to understand and respond to language, decisions, and problems.

Radixweb.com shows that over 1.1 billion people are expected to use AI by 2031, making it one of the fastest-adopted and used technologies in history. AI has touched different professional and non-professional fields and its usage depend on users' technological versatility. Scientists, engineers, marketers, bankers, business men, academia, artisans including men of Pen Profession (journalism) find AI invaluable to get their work done. Artificial Intelligence has technologically and perfectly been programmed for easy accessibility, analysis (processes) and distribution (output). It is a known fact that users' understanding of how AI work is a major determining factor in getting desired results. So, people must adequately understand the workings of AI so that the outcome will be more reliable and dependable. Specifically, Fei-Fei Li (2025) said AI governance should be based on science rather than science-fiction.

The records show that market for AI technology is vast, amounting to around 371 billion U.S. dollars in 2025 (Market and Markets) and is expected to grow well beyond that to over 757 billion U.S. dollars by 2030 (Precedence Research). Russell and Norvig (2020) affirmed that AI is broadly divided into machine learning and deep learning. These then have further subcategories such as natural language processing, computer vision, robotics, and more. Machine learning constitutes the most basic and simple AI form. Programs operating on machine learning are given a clear set of parameters to use in interactions with humans and are limited in scope. It is also the most common form of AI, used in basic chat assistants, apps, voice commands, and other limited engagements.

Deep learning is closer to what a person would imagine from AI. In deep learning programs, AI has initial parameters and datasets but can integrate user information as it interacts with humans. In this way, the AI learns as it is used, becoming more sophisticated in the process. Recent examples of advanced deep learning programs are OpenAI's ChatGPT and Google's Gemini. (Thormundsson, 2025).

In January, 2025, Vanguard Newspaper in Nigeria published a research report that Nigeria surpasses global average with 70% AI adoption rate. The report said Nigeria's online population is leading the global adoption of generative AI, with 70 percent of respondents reporting usage, far exceeding the global average of 48 percent. The report is according to a global survey by Paris-based research firm Ipsos in collaboration with Google.

The study, titled "Our Life with AI: From Innovation to Application," surveyed 21,000 people across 21 countries. It revealed a growing global acceptance of AI, with 57 per cent of respondents expressing excitement about its potential compared to 43 percent who remain cautious. Report showed Nigeria's AI adoption; 70% of the online population have used generative AI. 87% believe AI's benefits outweigh its risks. 90% anticipate positive impacts in science and medicine. 81% foresee economic transformation driven by AI.

With this report, Nigerians dependence on AI is quite alarming and it is of believe that AI is gradually taken over human creativity and existence. Adoption and implementation of AI is good, no doubt, but over reliance on its usage is a great concern to human creativity and development. Therefore, this paper is set out to analyze and make inform decision in the interest of human race.

Statement of the Problem

The use of AI provides desirable results as it is faster in its implementation, details and organized information in all fields of life. It also reduces human stress of searching for reliable and dependable empirical evidences. Despite these great benefits of artificial intelligence in our modern world, it is still difficult to deny quite number of challenges AI has brought to human life. Many observers and media professionals said AI has not only created lack of transparency and trust in the information generation and distribution, AI has led to job displacement as well as a strong artificial factor in reduction of human creativity and capacity development in the field of journalism.

These areas of creativity and capacity development formed great concern and require critical observation and analysis in order to reshape the world and make it a better place for the benefit of humanity. Most journalists now rely much more on AI in sourcing for facts and figures. Surprisingly, AI has become a writing tool for many journalists including experience members of fourth estate of the realm. These actions kill human creativity and capacity development in all strata of journalistic practices. The study is determined to see what AI has done and what it is doing to the journalism profession, most importantly in the area of creativity and capacity development.

This research main's objective is to assess the impact of AI on media practitioners' creativity and specific objectives are;

- a. To ascertain rate of AI usage among media professionals
- b. To verify if AI usage reduces journalists' creative ability and capacity development?
- c. To know whether media stations can survive public demand without AI?
- d. To investigate whether adoption of AI by media practitioners affect professional standard

This study is set to answer the following Research Questions:

- a. What is the rate of AI usage among media professionals?
- b. Does AI reducing journalists' creative ability and capacity development?
- c. Can media stations survive public demand without AI?
- d. Is adoption of AI by media practitioners affecting professional standard?

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Artificial Intelligence (AI) refers to the simulation of human intelligence in machines that are programmed to think, learn, and solve problems. AI systems can process vast amounts of data, recognize patterns, and make informed decisions, often surpassing human capabilities in speed and accuracy (Russell & Norvig, 2021). AI applications range from simple automation to advanced machine learning algorithms capable of self-improvement.

AI has been integrated into various industries, including healthcare, finance, education, and entertainment, fundamentally transforming human interactions with technology. AI has profound implications for humanity, influencing employment, ethics, education, and healthcare. It enhances productivity and innovation, yet concerns about job displacement, privacy, and bias remain prevalent (Tegmark, 2017). AI is reshaping the labor market by automating routine jobs while creating new opportunities in emerging fields. Ethical concerns include the accountability of AI decisions, biases in machine learning models, and the risk of surveillance misuse (Bostrom, 2014). Scholars emphasize the need for human-centered AI development that prioritizes fairness, transparency, and inclusivity.

Journalists and media practitioners generally rely on information or contents to discharge their civic responsibilities. The information is generated from the society, processed and return back to the people in the same society. But, in a modern and technologically programmed society, AI has engulfed and occupied every aspect of life. In fact, media men have turned to AI drastically for their content's generations. This is a great concern to professional practice. It is a known fact that credible source is essential for authentic information. therefore, journalist must get to the source and get the fact before given it out to the public. This action promotes critical thinking, skills and techniques thereby enhance human creativity and nurture journalist's capacity development.

In 2010, Nicholans Carr analyzed the power of technology, especially internet and he noted that technology has reshaped and still reshaping our minds. Internet and indeed, AI is reshaping every institution and human life, thereby making creativity and capacity development facing great challenge as technology is evolving every day. Runco and Jaeger (2012) say human creativity is the mental ability to produce original, imaginative, and valuable ideas, artifacts, or solutions. It is considered a fundamental human trait that contributes to innovation, culture, art, science, and technology.

Creativity encompasses divergent thinking, cognitive flexibility, intuition, and insight. It enables individuals to challenge existing paradigms, explore new possibilities, and make unique contributions to society. Whether through artistic expression, scientific exploration, or entrepreneurial innovation, creativity is integral to human development and cultural evolution.

Psychologists and cognitive scientists view creativity as both a process and a product. It is on this premise that Csikszentmihalyi (1996) opines that creativity involves complex interactions between knowledge, experience, personality, and environment. Creative individuals often exhibit openness to experience, intrinsic motivation, and the ability to make connections between seemingly unrelated concepts. Creativity is not limited to the arts; it plays a vital role in problem-solving, critical thinking, and adapting to change across various domains of life. In the context of an AI-driven world, preserving and fostering human creativity remains crucial to maintaining human agency and emotional depth.

Morgan (2006) describes capacity development as process of strengthening the abilities, skills, resources, and institutions that individuals, organizations, and societies need to survive, adapt, and thrive in a fast-changing world. It is a holistic approach that involves building competencies at various levels individual, organizational, and systemic to achieve sustainable outcomes. This process is not limited to formal education or training; it also encompasses informal learning, experience-sharing, and organizational culture reform that foster continuous growth and adaptability.

At the individual level, capacity development focuses on enhancing knowledge, technical skills, and leadership abilities. It aims to empower people to participate fully in their professional and civic life by equipping them with tools for problem-solving and decision-making. For example, training programs for healthcare workers, digital literacy initiatives, and leadership development workshops contribute to human capital formation, which is essential for national progress and innovation (Lusthaus et al., 2002).

On an organizational and institutional level, capacity development addresses the policies, structures, systems, and practices that support effective functioning. This may involve improving management systems, fostering a culture of accountability, strengthening legal frameworks, and ensuring access to essential resources. When institutions are strong and efficient, they can drive inclusive growth, good governance, and service delivery. Thus, capacity development is a critical enabler of resilience, equity, and sustainable development (UNDP, 2009).

Evaluating AI from positive angle, it must be stated that it;

- a. **Enhanced Learning:** AI-powered education tools provide personalized learning experiences, adapting to individual student needs and improving learning outcomes.
- b. **Improved Productivity:** AI assists in automating complex tasks, increasing efficiency and reducing errors in various sectors
- c. **Innovation Stimulation:** AI aids in creative processes by generating ideas, analyzing trends, and optimizing workflows (Boden, 2004).

As good as AI, based on facts provided above, it has tremendous effects on human existence and the fact is hereby presented;

- a. **Job Displacement:** AI automation threatens traditional jobs, particularly in manufacturing, retail, and customer service
- b. **Dependency on Technology:** Over-reliance on AI may lead to a decline in critical thinking and problem-solving skills among individuals
- c. **Ethical Concerns:** Bias in AI models can reinforce social inequalities, leading to unfair treatment in areas such as hiring, lending, and law enforcement
- d. **Security Risks:** AI-powered cyber threats pose risks to data privacy, cybersecurity, and national security (Brundage et al., 2018).

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

The study of AI and human capacity development can be analyzed using several theoretical perspectives. Most relevant theories to this study are, technological determinism theory and human capital theory. However, this paper is anchored on technological determinism theory as it is not only relevant to the study by emphasizing on contributions of technology to media practices, it also elucidates on effects of overreliance on technology in all institutions and human lives.

Technological Determinism – This theory posits that technology shapes societal progress and influences human behavior (McLuhan, 1964). Technological determinism suggests that advances in technology are the primary driver of changes in culture, society, and human development. In the context of AI, this theory highlights how automation, machine learning, and robotics reshape labor markets, redefine social norms, and influence educational paradigms.

Although technological determinism has been both praised and criticized, as advocates argue that technological advancement is inevitable and largely beneficial, promoting efficiency and progress. Critics, however, caution against over-reliance on technology as a one-way force, ignoring the role of human agency and ethical responsibility. They warn that without proper regulation and consideration of societal impacts; AI could exacerbate inequalities and lead to unintended consequences.

Human Capital Theory – Developed by Gary Becker (1964), this theory posits that investments in education, skills, and health increase an individual's productivity and potential to contribute economically. In the context of AI, this theory underscores the importance of continuous learning and capacity building to remain relevant in a technology-driven economy. Individuals who develop AI-related competencies are better equipped to adapt to new job roles and contribute meaningfully to society.

AI has also reshaped how human capital is developed and measured. Adaptive learning platforms, virtual training environments, and AI-driven assessment tools provide personalized educational experiences, accelerating skill acquisition. However, this also raises concerns about accessibility and equity, as not all populations may have equal access to these advanced tools. Human Capital Theory thus reinforces the need for inclusive capacity development policies that leverage AI for broader social benefit.

METHODOLOGY

As a descriptive research study, this study focused on media practitioners most especially, journalists, on their usage of AI and implications on professional job. Survey research method and In-depth interview research method were strictly adopted to get responses from men of fourth estate of the realm.

The survey research method was specifically designed to focus on 120 respondents (journalists) in three selected states in southwest, Nigeria, namely; Osun, Oyo and Lagos, were conveniently drawn and given structured questionnaire electronically, 40 journalists were sampled from Osun, Oyo and Lagos respectively. In-depth-interview involved three (3) experienced editors from news outfits and these three respondents were purposively selected based on their academic qualification, professional training,

experience, and their media stations (one editor from print media, one editor from broadcast media and one editor from online news outlet), each respondent were selected from Osun, Oyo and Lagos respectively. The adoption of quantitative and qualitative research approaches, most especially involvement of three editors from different strata of journalism provided rich and dependable insights to validate the outcome of this research work.

The study covered four months (January, February, March and April, 2026).

Data Analysis

Quantitative (Survey)

Table 1: Research Questions One: What is the rate of AI usage among media professionals?

Variables	Description	Frequency	Percentage
How frequently do you use AI tools in your daily media work?	Never	0	0.00%
	Rarely (less than once a month)	11	9.17%
	Occasionally (1-3 times a month)	49	40.83%
	Frequently (1-3 times a week)	25	20.83%
	Very frequently (daily or multiple times a day)	35	29.17%
	TOTAL		120
Which AI tools do you commonly use in your media practice?	Content generation tools	64	53.33%
	Data analysis tools	20	16.67%
	Image/video editing AI	5	4.17%
	Transcription/speech-to-text AI	29	24.17%
	None	0	0.00%
	Other	2	1.67%
TOTAL		120	100%
On a scale of 1-5, how would you rate the integration of AI in your media organization?	1 (Not integrated at all)	3	2.50%
	2	13	10.83%
	3	76	63.33%
	4	8	6.67%
	5 (Fully integrated)	20	16.67%
	TOTAL		120

Source: Survey Data, 2026

ANALYSIS:

From the analysis above in table 1, it indicates 49 (40.83%) respondents representing majority said they use AI tools in their daily media work occasionally (1-3 times a month), 64 (53.33%) respondents representing majority said content generation tools are AI tools they commonly use in their media practice while 76 (63.33%) respondents representing majority said rated the integration of AI in their media organization in 3 out of 1-5. Therefore, majority of the respondents agreed that they use AI tools in their daily media work occasionally, content generation tools are AI tools they commonly use in their media practice and partially rated the integration of AI in their media organization.

Table 2. Research Questions Three: Does AI wiping journalists’ creative ability and capacity development?

Variables	Description	Frequency	Percentage
To what extent do you agree that AI reduces the need for original creative thinking in journalism?	Strongly disagree	15	12.50%
	Disagree	32	26.67%
	Neutral	8	6.67%
	Agree	55	45.83%
	Strongly agree	10	8.33%
	TOTAL	120	100%
Has using AI improved your skills in areas like research or content production?	Yes, significantly	24	20.00%
	Yes, moderately	78	65.00%
	No change	5	4.17%
	No, it has hindered my skills	7	5.83%
	I don't use AI	6	5.00%
	TOTAL	120	100%
Do you believe AI tools limit journalists' capacity to develop unique storytelling abilities?	Yes	24	20.00%
	No	48	40.00%
	Maybe	48	40.00%
	TOTAL	120	100%

Source: Survey Data, 2026

ANALYSIS:

From the analysis above in table 2, it indicates 55 (45.83%) respondents representing majority agreed that AI reduces the need for original creative thinking in journalism; 78 (65.00%) respondents representing majority said using AI moderately improved their skills in areas like research or content production while 96 (80.00%) respondents representing majority could not agree whether AI tools limit journalists' capacity to develop unique storytelling abilities. Therefore, majority of the respondents agreed that AI reduces the need for original creative thinking in journalism, using AI moderately improved journalists' skills in areas like research or content production and it was undecided whether AI tools limit journalists' capacity to develop unique storytelling abilities.

Table 3. Research Questions three: Can media stations survive public demand without AI?

Variables	Description	Frequency	Percentage
Can media stations meet public demands for rapid, accurate content without AI?	Strongly disagree	3	2.50%
	Disagree	7	5.83%
	Neutral	5	4.17%
	Agree	80	66.67%
	Strongly agree	25	20.83%
	TOTAL	120	100%
How has AI helped your media station handle increasing public demands?	Faster content creation	46	38.33%
	Better audience targeting	46	38.33%
	Improved efficiency	23	19.17%
	No impact	5	4.17%

	Negative impact	0	0.00%
	TOTAL	120	100%
Without AI, would your media work be able to keep up with audience expectations?	Strongly disagree	0	0.00%
	Disagree	3	2.50%
	Neutral	18	15.00%
	Agree	69	57.50%
	Strongly agree	30	25.00%
	TOTAL	120	100%

Source: Survey Data, 2026

ANALYSIS:

From the analysis above in table 3, it indicates 80 (66.67%) respondents representing majority agreed that media stations meet public demands for rapid, accurate content without AI; 92 (76.66%) respondents representing majority said AI helped media station handle increasing public demands with Faster content creation and better audience targeting, lastly 69 (57.50%) respondents representing majority agreed that media work can keep up with audience without AI. Therefore, majority of the respondents agreed that media stations meet public demands for rapid, accurate content without AI, AI helped media station handle increasing public demands with faster content creation and better audience targeting and lastly, media work can keep up with audience without AI.

Table 4. Research Questions four: Is adoption of AI by media practitioners affect professional standard?

Variables	Description	Frequency	Percentage
Does the adoption of AI in media affect ethical standards, such as accuracy and bias?	Yes	18	15.00%
	No	79	65.83%
	Maybe	23	19.17%
	TOTAL	120	100%
To what extent has AI adoption changed professional training or standards in your field?	1 (No change)	2	1.67%
	2	3	2.50%
	3	66	55.00%
	4	23	19.17%
	5 (Significant change)	26	21.67%
	TOTAL	120	100%

Source: Survey Data, 2026

ANALYSIS:

From the analysis above in table 4, it indicates 79 (65.8367%) respondents representing majority agreed that adoption of AI in media affect ethical standards, such as accuracy and bias while 66 (55.00%) respondents representing majority said AI adoption averagely changed professional training or standards in their field. Therefore, majority of the respondents agreed that adoption of AI in media affect ethical standards, such as accuracy and bias, and lastly, AI adoption averagely changed professional training or standards in their field.

Qualitative (In-depth Interview)

Research Question a: How often do media professionals use AI?

The field responses show that the adoption of AI on the different media platforms in Nigeria is not evenly spread. *Participant 1* also indicated that in smaller regional contexts such as Osun, the use is relatively low projected at about 30-40, with tools only being used to simple features such as grammar checking or headline suggestions because most professionals still prefer the old-fashioned approach. In broadcast media, where AI is deployed in Oyo State, *participant 2* reported adoption of about 60% of

tasks, such as transcription, script writing, and voice text preparation, and is competition-driven, such as elections, but the resources needed to integrate AI are too limited in smaller stations. According to *participant 3*, in the online news media, especially in hectic Lagos, it is heavily used with usage rates of between 85-90, and AI is actively used in creating draughts, optimizing search engines, social media posts, and fact-checking to meet the fast deadlines and expectations of the audience.

Research Question b: Does AI erase the ability and capacity building of journalists in terms of creativity?

Participant 1 pointed out that overreliance on AI in the print media contextualizing the complete generation of stories will tend to homogenize style of writing and diminish personal voice, which may not lead to deep thinking and skill development, but can be effective as a learning aid to novice writers when used sparingly. *Participant 2* replied that broadcast professionals note that although AI can give rapid ideas, creative aspects such as the ability to deliver emotion and unusual on-ground shots are human-led; it supports capacity by demonstrating new skills such as being able to prompt effectively, but when applied sluggishly it results in reduced independent thinking. *Participant 3* appears to agree that the effect is situational: mass copying creates homogenous, soulless text that destroys creativity, but used strategically, gains time to do more complexity, and ultimately challenges but does not eliminate skills when coupled with human oversight.

Research Question c: Do media stations live without AI under the impact of the crowd?

According to the interviewees' responses, it is possible to survive without AI, but it becomes more difficult with each type of the media. Their audiences tolerate slow production and therefore, *participant 1* can fulfil the demand, albeit with significant use of traditional editing and robust editorial procedures, but they will risk falling behind on speed when major breaking news break, losing readers to other speedy platforms. *Participant 2* insisted that the broadcast stations have more hard work to do, since the performances with high expectations of the population to stay abreast of real-time information, videos, and high accuracy of the information require AI to be efficient; efforts to be made without it will lead to considerable delays and lost opportunities. *Participant 3* saw non-adoption as unsustainable on a 24/7 digital environment where there is a need of fresh content every minute to keep traffic and relevance, without AI, the volume of production will plummet and they will start losing competitiveness to other international and local outlets already using these tools.

Research Question d: Does the adoption of AI by media practitioners influence professional standard?

The interviews also emphasize that the adoption of AI can have a dual impact on professional standards, and the results of the application practices. *Participant 1* claims that uncontrolled use of it leads to decreased standards, including factual error, plagiarism and low level of originality, but with stringent verification measures, including multi-editor reviews, quality, fairness and ethical integrity can still be preserved. The responses of the *participant 2* highlight the improvements, such as improved hate-speech avoidance in the scripts, and the losses, such as delivery by the robot and superficial investigations, and so training is necessary to make sure that AI complements and does not replace the main professionalism. *Participant 3* indicated that hasty online publishing of unedited AI material hastens false information and credibility threats, whereas when controlled i.e., with AI taking a small part of the stores, with high human editing and fact-checking, the research quality, language, and general standards are advanced, making outlets credible under strict rules. In general, the consequences depend on the ethical training, regulation, and the harmonious development of human-AI cooperation to protect the principles of journalism as its main pillars.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The survey of 120 media workers and in-depth interviews with three senior editors (print journalism in Osun, broadcast news in Oyo, and online journalism in Lagos) present an image of a slow but steady increase in AI contribution to Nigerian journalism. The use of AI is average in general and is highly inconsistent across media. According to the survey data, the majority of respondents (40.83) use AI tools just once (1-3 times a month), although content generation tools are the most widespread (53.33%). The level of organizational integration is very average (63.33% gave it a 3 out of 5). This tendency is verified by the editors: the use of AI is minimal (approximately 30-40%), despite being used in grammar and headlines, in print media in regional environments because many of them still rely on traditional approaches. Media shows broadcasts exhibit greater adoption (approximately 60%), particularly regarding transcription, script writing and voice preparation during periods of high pressure such as elections, but due to resource constraints smaller stations have a reduced adoption rate. The highest usage (85-90%) is recorded in online news in Lagos fast-paced, and AI constantly reviews first draughts, social media captions, and fact-checking to meet time-limited deadlines.

The results are not biased on creativity and capacity development but equal. Albeit with 45.83% of the respondents in the survey agreeing that AI diminishes the necessity of the original creative thought, 65% of them state that they have moderate skills improvement in research and content production. A very significant proportion (80 percent) have no opinion as to whether AI restricts original storytelling. Adding depth by the editors: heavy use in print may flatten the style of writing and cause loss of personal voice, but judicious use can teach beginners to learn more quickly. In broadcast, AI can provide nipsy ideas, not human feelings, not on-ground angles, not independent thinking, lazy adoption lowers capacity, and thoughtful prompting new skills are formed. Mass copying in online media results in homogenous dead contents whereas with human controls, time can be saved to investigate and be more creative. In general, AI does not kill creativity; it will do so when applied in a disciplined and deliberate way.

On the survival in the absence of AI, survey participants are more than half that media stations will continue to fulfil the demand of the general population on fast and correct content (66.67% agreed), and on whether their work can adjust to the expectations of the audience with the absence of AI, the majority (82.5) of the respondents are assertive that they will be able to deliver. AI is perceived to be primarily helpful in accelerating the development process and targeting the audience more effectively. Editors provide a more modest opinion that is influenced by everyday realities. Print outlets are able to cope with good traditional editing but they lose pace on big storeys. Broadcast is also under the pressure of demanding real-time updates and videos- without AI, it cannot operate without delay. In an online environment, non-adoption is perceived to be unsustainable in a 24/7 digital world in which lack of new content will rapidly destroy traffic and relevance. The difference implies that lots of journalists believe that they can cope, whereas editors who run newsrooms feel the increasing competitive pressure.

Regarding the professional standards, 65.83% of the respondents indicate that AI does not influence the ethical issues like accuracy and bias, however, 55 percent report that training and standards are changed on average. There are dangers and protection, which are pointed out by the editors. Uncontrollable use during print leads to the introduction of factual mistakes and plagiarism, whereas multi editors check ensures it maintains levels of fairness and integrity. In broadcast, AI helps to eliminate hate speech in scripts, but in result can also generate robotic delivery and less in-depth reporting, which makes continuous organization training necessary. Hasty publication of unedited AI content disseminates misinformation in online contexts, whilst containing AI to a restricted section of the stories with high levels of human editing and fact-checking actually enhances the quality of research, grammar, and credibility. In all the avenues, the editors emphasize that ethical training, explicit regulations, and balanced human-AI interaction are essential to the safeguarding of fundamental values of journalism.

To conclude, both the quantitative and qualitative data can be aligned on moderate platform-specific AI adoption with beneficial but conditional outcomes. When applied improperly or excessively, AI increases the efficiency and some of the skills but poses a threat to originality, depth, and standards. Consideration, humanistic integration seems to be the most important in ensuring we maximize the benefits at the least possible losses in the practice of Nigerian media.

CONCLUSION

This paper has shown that the use of AI in the Nigerian media practitioners is increasing but at a moderate level with the majority of the respondents adopting it periodically, primarily as a content creation tool. Although the survey statistics reveal that people think that the media stations can continue to satisfy the needs of the population and do not need AI, those with experience in making decisions in such areas note that the work is becoming harder, especially in the context of the fast-paced broadcasting and online business where speed and quantity are paramount.

Artificial intelligence does not entirely eliminate the creativity and capacity-building efforts of journalists, and its effects will be determined by how it is used: over-use will homogenize creativity, but when it is used strategically, it will strengthen efficiency, research abilities, and more in-depth coverage. Uncontrolled, professional standards are threatened by mistakes, bias, or robot work, but are ensured by effective editorial control, checking, and education.

Essentially, AI is a strong supporting system but not a substitute of human journalists. A balanced integration, ethical standards, and long-term capacity building can help the Nigerian media to embrace the benefits of AI and remain creative, accurate, and trusted by the people as a quality news source.

RECOMMENDATIONS

To maximize the benefits of AI while mitigating its potential drawbacks, it is recommended that;

1. Media organizations ought to ensure that all their staff are trained on the ways of using AI intelligently, as an assistant and not a thinking substitute.
2. At least two editors should scrutinize every AI-generated content before it is published as this will help safeguard its accuracy and originality.
3. The media owners are expected to develop explicit policies on the use of AI to ensure that the level of professionalism remains uncompromised and also to take advantage of the opportunities of working at a faster pace.

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Cite this Article: Adeagbo, A., O Ayinla, O., Ewuola, O. P., Adesemowo, R. O. (2026). Assessment of Artificial Intelligence (AI) on Media Practitioners' Creativity and Capacity Development. International Journal of Current Science Research and Review, 9(5), pp. 2907-2916. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.47191/ijcsrr/V9-i5-62>